

IPBES BBA Chapter 6 - The role of Indigenous Peoples and local communities in transforming the enabling environment / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment

Code: IPBES_BBA_CH6_DMR_role_IPLCs

Version 03: (26.03.2026)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12787554>

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Description

This literature review corresponds to Chapter 6 of the IPBES business and biodiversity assessment. This review is based on keyword and snowball searches and was conducted to identify, characterize, and assess:

- 1) Why Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLCs) are essential in supporting measures of impacts and dependencies by business;
- 2) What are the options for action by these actors that can help efforts to create an enabling environment;
- 3) What are the barriers impeding these actions from happening;
- 4) How these actions can be used to create such an environment, including case studies where relevant.

This review focuses on actors from IPLCs and consists of thematic keyword searches of articles in Google Scholar, and material in the IPBES Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) library in Zotero as well as a snowball search performed by the IPBES Technical Support Unit on data and knowledge management.

Process overview

Stage 1

Stage 2

Protocol

i. Type of search: Snowball search for articles indexed in OpenAlex

- **Search engine:** OpenAlex
- **Search Date:** 18 December 2023
- **Key papers used to run the snowball search:** 14 expert-selected papers
- **Document containing key papers:** IPBES_BBA_6.1_07-2024_(A)
- **Sample extracted:** 1719 papers (B)
- **Document containing snowball corpus:** IPBES_BBA_6.1_07-2024_(B)

Treatment applied: Expert knowledge was used to select a list of 20 potential key materials in the field of Indigenous and local knowledge systems and in relation to six dimensions: political, legal, economic, social, technological and environmental. This followed initial discussions and the section structure agreed upon during the first author meeting for the assessment in September 2023. Of the potential 20 papers, 14 (A) were selected for a snowball search, as the remaining six did not have a DOI. The snowball search resulted in 1719 records (B).

ii. Type of search: Keyword searches

Following this initial material exploration, and considering the structure of section 6.3, the authors decided to run 13 thematic keyword searches (C) in the materials found on the snowball search (B), the IPBES Zotero library on Indigenous and local knowledge¹ and in Google Scholar search platform to identify, characterize and assess the four topics already outlined in the ‘Description’ section of this data management report.

1. A keyword search as described in C and adapted to Excel’s advanced research tool was applied to the 1719 results from the snowball search. A guide on advanced search in Excel can be found at <https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/filter-by-using-advanced-criteria-4c9222fe-8529-4cd7-a898-3f16abdf32b>.
2. A keyword search as described in C and adapted to Zotero’s advanced research tool was applied to the 5577 records indexed in the IPBES Zotero library on Indigenous and local knowledge. A guide on advanced search in Zotero can be found at <https://www.zotero.org/support/searchinghttps://www.zotero.org/support/searching>. We assumed that all material in the IPBES Zotero library on Indigenous and local knowledge already included material on Indigenous Peoples or local communities.
3. A keyword search as described in C was applied to papers indexed in the Google Scholar search platform.

¹ The IPBES Zotero library on Indigenous and local knowledge can be found here: https://www.zotero.org/groups/2344322/ipbes_indigenous_local_knowledge

- **Exact date of the searches:** All three searches were run throughout the writing process, between September 2023 (first author meeting) and July 2024 (External Review).
- **Search terms: (C)**

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND ("impacts" OR "dependence" OR "barriers") AND "business");

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "worldviews" AND ("pluralism" OR "democracy" OR "equity" OR "protagonism")));

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND ("territory demarcation" OR "self-determination" OR "land use rights")));

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND "legal framework");

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND "education" AND "empowerment");

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND "access" AND ("benefit sharing" OR "fairness")));

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND ("biopiracy" OR "patent" OR "intellectual rights")));

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND "technology" AND "infrastructure");

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND "product" AND "land use change" AND ("remote sensing" OR "traceability")));

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND "traditional knowledge" AND "knowledge transfer" AND "archives");

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND "collaborative" AND ("measures" OR "indicators") AND "worldviews");

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND ("economic development" OR "economic impacts") AND "social dependence");

((("indigenous" OR "local communities") AND "biodiversity" AND "impediments" AND "social cohesion")

Treatment applied: The titles and abstracts of the articles resulting from the 13 keyword searches were analysed for suitability. Articles were selected if they had relevant information to support answering the questions on which the keyword searches were based. Articles that had some of the keywords, but which content was considered as not helpful to answer the questions were excluded.

- **Sample extracted:** 133 records (D)

The resulting 133 papers were used as a literature base for the role of IPLCs in transforming the enabling environment. 17 papers came from the snowball list, 23 references from the ILK Zotero library and 93 from Google Scholar. The text was also supplemented with papers suggested through the external review.

Additional material used in section 6.3: Written contributions from two Indigenous contributing authors were used as complementary material to produce the text in section 6.3, see below:

- ❖ Carling, J. (2024). The role of Indigenous Peoples and local communities in encouraging businesses to protect nature. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12783142>
- ❖ Karmushu, R. (2024). Indigenous traditional knowledge, biodiversity conservation and nature-based businesses. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12664844>

Location and format of the data: Both contributions are in the business and biodiversity Zotero library together with the above-mentioned 133 records. More precisely, data is located in the Zotero library “Business and biodiversity assessment” > “Chapter 6” > “Section 6.3. IPLCs” collection.

Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_07-2024_(A)	.csv	4 KB	14 papers used to run the snowball search
B	IPBES_BBA_07-2024_(B)	.csv	2,768 KB	1719 papers resulting from snowball search
D	IPBES_BBA_07-2024_(D)	.csv	7,940 KB	133 papers